

Spectrophotometric Study of the Acid-Base Equilibria of Sudan Green in Mixed Water-Organic Solvent Media

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The visible absorption spectra of 1,4-di(4'-methyl-anilino)-8-hydroxyanthraquinone (sudan green) have been recorded in water-organic solvent mixtures in the pH range 0.2-11.5. The organic solvents used were ethanol, dimethylformamide and acetone. The spectral changes have been explained in terms of shifts in equilibria set between different molecular and ionic species existing in solution. The pK_a values corresponding to the different ionisation steps have been determined at 25° and ionic strength of 0.1 by graphical analysis of the absorbance-pH curves. The elimination of the proton from the α -OH group of the nonionised species of the reagent takes place below pH 4.5 as a result of mesomeric interaction between the imino nitrogen and the C-O group. Further insight about the acidobasic equilibria of sudan green is given using pH-metric titration. The results are discussed in terms of molecular structure of the reagent and nature of the organic co-solvent used.

In spite of the significant applications of amino- and arylamino-anthraquinones as histological or analytical reagents and as complexing or mordant agents, the acidobasic properties of only few of these compounds have been reported by Idriss *et al.*¹⁻⁴. Our previous work has shown that 1,4-bis(arylamino)anthraquinones have some advantages among the acid dyes of the anthraquinone group for further applications in analytical chemistry. Interest in the reactivity of quinizarin green (QG) with metal ions has increased considerably in recent years⁴⁻⁹.

Our continued interest in the solution equilibria of arylaminoanthraquinones, led us to undertake the study on the optical and acid-base characteristics of 1,4-bis(4-methyl-anilino)-8-hydroxyanthraquinone (sudan green, SG) in water-organic solvent mixtures. No report is found in the literature about this reagent. Our goal is to clarify the spectral changes occurring with pH change and to obtain a desirable level of control over the various acid-base equilibria existing in solution. The values of the acid dissociation constants have been determined whenever possible from the graphical analysis of the spectral data. An additional information was obtained from pH-titration of the reagent solution.

Experimental

Stock solutions of SG (2×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³) were prepared by dissolving the purified reagent in ethanol, dimethylformamide or acetone (spectrograde). All other chemicals were of analytical grade. Standard carbonate-free NaOH and perchloric acid solutions were prepared. Deionised water was used throughout. The working solutions were prepared by accurate dilution. The acidity of the measured

solutions was adjusted by dilute HClO₄ or by NaOH solution. The ionic strength (*I*) was maintained at constant value of 0.10 M (NaClO₄).

The absorption spectra were recorded on a Pye-Unicam SP 800J spectrophotometer at 25° using 1 cm matched stoppered quartz cells. pH measurements were carried out using a Radiometer M63 pH-meter equipped with Radiometer combined glass electrode. The pH values in mixed media were corrected as described by Douheret¹⁰.

Results and Discussion

Depending on the acidity of the medium, the solution of SG contains four optically different acid-base forms, LH₂²⁺, LH₂⁺, LH₂⁰ and LH₂⁻. The diprotonated species LH₂²⁺ (520 nm) is present in strong acid medium (pH < 0.3). In the pH 0.5-1.2 the solution contains the purple monoprotinated LH₂⁺ form (550 and 630 nm) together with the neutral LH₂⁰ form (pH > 1.5). Above pH 2, the spectra of SG exhibit a new absorption band at 440-460 nm. The longer wavelength band splits at 590 and 640 nm. The intensity of the band at 440 nm increases rapidly with the rise of pH whereas the absorption at 550 nm decreases gradually and vanishes completely at pH ~ 4.5. These spectral changes are assumed to accompany the transformation of the neutral form of SG (LH₂⁰) to the monoionised species LH₂⁻. The red LH₂⁰ species existing in pH 2-3.5 is converted to the pale green monoanionic form (LH₂⁻) at pH ~ 4.0, above which the solution spectra exhibit no band shift or intensity changes.

The acid-base equilibria of SG were studied in media containing 20, 50 and 75% of the organic

co-solvent (ethanol, DMF or acetone). The absorbance of $4 \times 10^{-5} M$ reagent solution in the presence of various concentrations of $HClO_4$ or $NaOH$ was recorded as the dependence $A=f(\lambda)$ for various pH. The spectral changes of SG with pH (Fig. 1) show

Fig. 1 Dependence of absorption spectra of SG on acidity; $C_L = 4 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, 50% DMF. pH curves: (1) 0.3, (2) 0.8, (3) 1.85, (4) 2.02, (5) 2.22, (6) 2.50, (7) 2.78, (8) 2.95, (9) 3.30, (10) 3.60, (11) 3.80, (12) 3.90, (13) 4.15, (14) 4.55, (15) 5.95 and (16) 7.90.

three isosbestic points (near 575, 560 and 495 nm) denoting different equilibria in solution. The curves of the absorption spectra for the individual acid-base forms (in 50% ethanol) measured in the acidity region where the existence of a single acid-base form of SG can be assumed are given in (Fig. not shown for brevity). The dissociation constant values of SG in various media were evaluated for the individual formation regions of the absorbance-pH curves (Fig. not shown) by graphical analysis.

The principles of the graphical treatment of data are given elsewhere¹¹⁻¹³. For the sake of brevity we shall give only the final equations. The transformations are derived from the equation for the equilibrium constant and mass balance equations, combined with the equation for total absorbance of the solution (assuming the validity of Beer's law). After simple rearrangement one obtains

for the equilibrium (A) the following transformations,

$$\epsilon_1 \quad \epsilon_2$$

$$A = \epsilon_1 C_L + K_{\alpha} (\epsilon_2 C_L - A) / [H^+] = A_{01} + F_1 K_{\alpha} \quad (1)$$

$$A - \epsilon_2 C_L - (A - \epsilon_1 C_L) K_{\alpha}^{-1} [H^+] = A_{02} - F_2 K_{\alpha}^{-1} \quad (2)$$

$$C_L/A = 1/\epsilon_1 - (C_L \epsilon_2 - A) [H^+]^{-1} A^{-1} \epsilon_1^{-1} K_{\alpha} = \epsilon_1^{-1} - Q [H^+]^{-1} \quad (3)$$

$$C_L/A = 1/\epsilon_2 + (A - C_L \epsilon_1) [H^+] A^{-1} \epsilon_2^{-1} K_{\alpha}^{-1} - \epsilon_2^{-1} + Q [H^+] \quad (4)$$

where, A is the absorbance, C_L the total reagent concentration, ϵ_1 and ϵ_2 are molar absorption coefficients, K_{α} is the equilibrium constant of the reaction (A), and the other symbols are self-explanatory.

By plotting $A=f(F_1 \text{ or } F_2)$ or $C_L/A=f(Q[H^+]^{-1} \text{ or } Q[H^+])$ straight lines were obtained. The values of the dissociation constant can then be obtained from the slope. More precise values of K could be evaluated by using the 'graphical logarithmic analysis'. The corresponding equation can be derived from any of the equations (1-4) in the form (5),

$$\log \frac{A - \epsilon_1 C_L}{\epsilon_2 L - A} = q \text{ pH} - pK_{\alpha} \quad (5)$$

The slope of the plots of $\log [(A - A_{01}) / (A_{02} - A)] - f(\text{pH})$ gives the number of protons (q) liberated in the acid-base equilibrium ($q-1$ for reaction A). The value of pH at which $\log [(A - A_{01}) / (A_{02} - A)]$ is equal to zero determines the value of pK_{α}/q . The procedure described above was applied separately to each wavelength and from the series of pK_{α} values the mean values were calculated. Deviation from the mean pK values were evaluated using equation (6)

$$\sigma(pK) = \left(\frac{1}{N-1} \sum_{n=1}^{N_{\lambda}} (p\bar{K} - pK_n)^2 \right)^{1/2} \quad (6)$$

where, pK is the mean value calculated from pK values obtained from curves for individual wavelength n , and N_{λ} the number of wavelengths used. The acid-base and optical characteristics of SG are illustrated in Table 1. Below pH 0.4, the spectrum of SG consists mainly of quite symmetrical band with λ_{max} at $\sim 520 \text{ nm}$. This band undergoes red-shift and an apparent decrease of intensity on decreasing the acidity of the medium. At pH 2.5-4, the spectra of the reagent display an absorption at $\sim 460 \text{ nm}$ which is blue-shifted with the rise of pH. In addition, two overlapped bands are well-defined at 590 and 640 nm, the latter one makes its first appearance at pH ~ 1.2 .

The appearance of only one main absorption band at lower pH's can be ascribed to the localisation of the π -electrons of the imino nitrogen

TABLE 1—ACID—BASE AND SPECTRAL CHARACTERISTICS OF SG IN VARIOUS MEDIA

Solvent %	pK _a *		λ _{isosbestic}			λ _{max} , nm (ε _{max} , × 10 ⁻⁴ mol cm ⁻²)		
	(LH ₂ ⁺ /LH ₂ ⁰)	(LH ₂ ⁰ /LH ₂ ⁻)	LH ₂ ⁺ /LH ₂ ⁰	LH ₂ ⁰ /LH ₂ ⁻	LH ₂ ⁰ /LH ₂ ⁻	LH ₂ ⁺	LH ₂ ⁰	LH ₂ ⁻
Ethanol—Water								
20	1.85±0.03	3.72±0.01	573	560	498	54 (1.5)	633 (0.5)	453 (2.25)
50	2.33±0.01	3.75±0.01	570	562	497	545 (1.55)	638 (1.35)	456 (2.38)
75	2.45±0.02	3.85±0.03	570	560	596	545 (1.6)	636 (1.42)	455 (2.38)
DMF—Water								
20	1.75±0.02	3.67±0.03	570	560	498	544 (1.63)	635 (1.25)	458 (2.33)
50	2.18±0.01	3.65±0.01	574	560	495	545 (1.63)	638 (1.30)	453 (2.45)
75	2.38±0.02	3.55±0.02	576	562	492	546 (1.45)	637 (1.13)	450 (2.23)
Acetone—Water								
20	2.04±0.03	3.74±0.01	575	560	494	540 (2.25)	635 (1.70)	455 (2.23)
50	2.34±0.03	3.85±0.02	575	562	495	542 (2.50)	638 (1.70)	456 (2.43)
75	^a	3.88±0.01	572	564	498	542 (2.55)	636 (1.70)	458 (2.35)

*Values resulting as a mean from the values calculated for each wavelength using equation (5).

^apK_a value could not be determined.

whereas the separation into two bands is due to the interaction of these electrons with the π-electrons of the aromatic system. The band at ~460 nm can be assigned as the π-π* intramolecular charge transfer associated with the charge migration from the substituents to the anthraquinone moiety. The blue-shift of this band on increasing the pH is due to the blocking of the lone-pair of electrons of the N atoms which leads to hindrance of the charge transfer resulting in higher excitation energy.

The spectral changes of SG with pH show three distinct isosbestic points denoting particular acidobasic equilibria. These equilibria can be represented as

The appearance of the two overlapped bands on the longer wavelength side at pH ~1.2 and the obvious decrease of intensity of the π-π* transition band at 280 nm corresponding to the quinonoid system suggest that the reagent SG in its monocationic form is involved in a resonance interaction of the type.

Such equilibrium seems to be shifted to the right at pH ~2. This assumption gives an explanation for the spectral changes accompanying the liberation of the proton from α-OH group which takes place at pH 3.5-4. The band at 520 nm becomes

ill-defined at pH > 4 presumably due to the transformation of the neutral form of the reagent (LH₂⁰) to the monoanionic species (LH₂⁻). The removal of the proton from the α-OH group leads to hindering the ionisation of the mesomeric form (II) of the reagent. This is evidenced by the non-existent spectral changes above pH ~5.

An attempt was made to ascertain the ability of proton dissociation from the LH₂⁻ species using pH-metric titration, 50 cm³ of 2.5 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³ HClO₄ and NaClO₄ (I = 100 mmol dm⁻³) were titrated in the presence and absence of the reagent SG (10⁻⁴ mol dm⁻³). The titration was performed in 50% (v/v) ethanol, DMF or acetone-water medium. The titration graph (Fig. not shown) of SG in its monoanionic form (LH₂⁻) gives only one step inflection at C_{OH}/C_L = 1, where C_{OH} is the equivalent base added and C_L the total initial concentration of SG. Multi-titrations were carried out in the media investigated. The inflection obtained was found always to start at pH 8-8.5. This inflection is unambiguously due to the dissociation of the proton from LH₂⁻ species and the production of doubly ionised form (LH₂²⁻) of the compound.

It is therefore not surprising that the LH₂⁻ species is the prevalent form of SG in the entire pH interval 4.5-8. In this respect, it is worthy to mention that the last proton elimination is not accompanied by measurable changes in the recorded spectra of the compound in different media (Fig. 1). This behaviour can be explained on the bases that the N-phenyl moiety is twisted out of the plane of the rest of the molecule^{14,15}. This results in a weak electronic interaction of the N-phenyl group with the anthraquinone nucleus. Accordingly, one can assume that the acid dissociation occurring at pH ≥ 8.5 is due to the liberation of the proton from the anilino group. The above conclusion may give an insight about the complexing forming ability of SG when present in its divalent anionic form.

TABLE 2—VALUES OF ACID DISSOCIATION CONSTANT (LH_2^-/ LH^-) OF SG IN 50% (v/v) WATER-ORGANIC SOLVENT MIXTURES FROM pH-METRIC TITRATION $I = 100 \text{ mmol dm}^{-3}$ (NaClO_4), Temp. = 25°

Solvent	pK_a
Ethanol	9.50
DMF	9.35
Acetone	9.79

Solvent effect on pK_a values: The results (Tables 1 and 2) indicate that the variation of pK_a values in solutions containing the same percentage of the different organic solvent follow the order, DMF < ethanol < acetone. This is presumably due to the decrease in the tendency of the solvent to associate with the solute through H-bond. Acetone is characterised by a very weak tendency to donate hydrogen bond¹⁶. The pK_a values obtained in the poorer donor-hydrogen bond DMF is less than those obtained in presence of ethanol due to the high basic character of the former solvent, which leads to facilitating the ionisation process.

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